

Mechanisms of Using Modern Pedagogical Technologies in the Educational Process

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Annotation: *In this article, the stages of organizing the educational process using innovative technologies of teaching in modern society were analyzed. Nowadays, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing year by year.*

Key words: *method, innovation, novation, pedagogical technology, modern education, attention, education, interactive methods, thought, IT.*

Modern pedagogical technologies provide an opportunity to make the educational process more effective, interesting and interactive. They help students to acquire deeper knowledge, develop independent thinking, increase their tendency to self-learning and form competencies that meet the requirements of the 21st century. Today, one of the reasons for the development of modern pedagogical technologies is that, until now, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made, uniform knowledge, but modern technologies allow them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, independently, teaches them to analyze and even draw their own conclusions. In such a process, teachers and students create conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of a person, and at the same time, they perform the functions of management and guidance. Students become the main figure in the educational process. Therefore, modern teaching methods and interactive methods are effectively used in the training of qualified professionals and specialists in higher educational institutions and faculties. In the process of applying innovative technologies to the educational process, the relationship between the student and the teacher comes to the fore. Pedagogical technology and knowledge, experience and interactive methods of the pedagogue's skills ensure that the students acquire educated and mature skills.

Modern innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and in its implementation mainly interactive methods are fully used. Interactive methods are called collective thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and students.

Such a process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- a) forcing the student not to be indifferent during classes, to think independently, to create and search;
- b) to ensure that pupils-students are constantly interested in knowledge during the educational process;
- c) increase the student's interest in knowledge by independently approaching each issue creatively;
- d) Always cooperative activities of pedagogue and pupil-student organization.

In the opinion of teachers, masters, independent researchers, practitioners studying the issues and problems of pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is not only related to information technology, but also IT, computer, defined as distance learning or the use of different techniques. In our opinion, the most important basis of modern pedagogical technologies is that it depends on the selected technologies for the teacher and student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal in cooperation that is, guaranteed by the goal in the process of teaching and knowledge. every educational technology used to achieve the result can organize a cooperative activity between the teacher and the student, both can achieve a positive result, if the students can think independently and work positively during the learning process, if they can analyze what they are looking for, if they can make their own conclusions, if they can evaluate themselves, the group, and the group can evaluate them, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for such activities, in our opinion, this is the basis of the teaching process. Each lesson, practical training, seminar training, topic, educational subject has its own characteristics and technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is It is purposeful, pre-planned and guaranteed. The realization of the goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result depend on the cooperative activity of both the teacher and the student, the goal they set, the chosen content, method, form, tool, that is, technology. It is up to the teacher and the student-student to choose the technology and methods to achieve the set goal, because the main goal chosen by both sides is clear: to achieve results and efficiency, in which the student-student's level of knowledge, group character, condition- the technology used is chosen depending on the situation, for example, it may be necessary to work with a computer to achieve the result, perhaps a film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology are needed, it depends on the teacher and the student, of course. In addition, it is necessary to design the teaching process, the training in advance, in this process the teacher organizes the specific aspect of the educational subject, place and conditions, most importantly, the opportunity and need of the student, as well as cooperative activities. should be taken into account, only then, the desired guaranteed result can be achieved. In short, it should bring the student to the center of education. It is necessary for the teacher to be able to see each lesson as a whole and to design the future lesson process in order to imagine it. It is very important for the teacher to make a technological map of the upcoming lesson. Because the technological map of the lessons and trainings is created based on the nature of the subject, the subject being taught for each topic, each lesson, and the possibilities and needs of the students.

The following are important for effective use of modern pedagogical technologies:

- Development of teachers' skills in working with these technologies;
- Smart selection and use of technologies in the educational process;
- Taking into account the individual characteristics of students;
- Application of technologies at all stages of the educational process;
- Development of students' skills to work with modern technologies.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies makes the educational process more effective and interesting, deepens students' knowledge and forms competencies that meet the requirements of the 21st century. The technology card prepared by the teacher for each topic of the subject, each lesson, helps him to visualize and understand the subject and the subject as a whole, the beginning of the whole educational process, the result to be achieved. helps him to see. In particular, the construction of the technological card based on the possibilities and needs of the student leads to bringing him as a person to the center of education. This makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of teaching. In the process of teaching, students are treated as individuals, various pedagogical technologies and modern methods are used to enable them to think independently, freely, to research, to approach each

issue creatively, to feel responsibility, to conduct scientific research, to analyze scientific literature. to use the phone effectively, and most importantly, to increase interest in reading, science, pedagogy, and the profession of his choice.

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